

The Regulatory Environment in the Global Innovation Index

Angelo Leogrande, Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, leogrande.cultore@lum.it

The variable "Regulatory environment" in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) represents a key factor that measures the quality and effectiveness of a country's regulatory framework in promoting innovation. This variable evaluates the existence of laws, regulations, and policies that either facilitate or hinder the development of innovative ideas and their practical application. A favorable regulatory environment is characterized by rules that encourage intellectual property protection, simplify the starting and management of new businesses, and ensure a stable and predictable legal system. Additionally, it considers the efficiency and transparency of public institutions responsible for implementing these regulations. A strong regulatory framework not only provides fertile ground for the emergence and growth of new technologies and processes but also attracts both domestic and international investments necessary for innovation progress. For example, countries with well-developed intellectual property systems better protect inventions and innovations, encouraging companies to invest in research and development. Furthermore, a flexible regulatory environment can quickly adapt to technological changes, creating conditions for the rise of new industries and business models. However, an overly rigid or complex regulatory environment can hinder innovation. Strict or inconsistent regulations may slow the introduction of new products or services, limit entrepreneurship, and discourage technological experimentation. In summary, the "Regulatory environment" variable in the GII offers a measure of a country's ability to create and maintain a regulatory framework that supports innovation, balancing legal protection and economic freedom to stimulate innovative growth.

Regulatory Environment in 2022. The provided data offers a comprehensive overview of the regulatory environments of various countries in 2022, highlighting a diverse range of performances in terms of governance, transparency, and institutional quality. These factors are crucial as they directly impact the ease of doing business, protection of rights, and the stability necessary for economic growth and development. At the top of the ranking, Singapore, with an impressive score of 98.7, stands out as a global leader in the regulatory environment. This aligns with Singapore's reputation for having a highly efficient, transparent, and well-structured government. Its regulatory framework facilitates economic activities, ensures property rights protection, and promotes low corruption levels, making it an attractive country for both domestic and international investors. Following Singapore, New Zealand (96.7), Finland (95.7), and Norway (95.6) also display robust regulatory environments. These countries are known for their high standards of governance, where transparency, rule of law, and administrative efficiency are key elements of their economic success. Hong Kong (94.2), with its well-developed regulatory framework, maintains a high position thanks to its economic openness and regulatory efficiency, although it has faced political challenges in recent years. Austria (93.2) and Switzerland (92.4) continue to exemplify excellence in continental Europe, with strong regulatory systems that ensure effective governance, economic stability, and legal protection, all factors that support sustainable growth. Outside of Western countries, nations such as Japan (91.1), Canada (91.5), and Australia (90.8) also exhibit advanced regulatory environments, showing that a well-developed regulatory framework is essential for maintaining global economic competitiveness. The United States (89.4) and the United Kingdom (90.4) remain among the top-

performing countries, although slightly behind other leading nations. The U.S., in particular, faces criticism for the complexity of its regulatory system and lack of consistency at the federal level. Lower down in the rankings, countries like Italy (77.5) and Germany (79.3) have advanced regulatory systems but often face challenges related to bureaucracy and slow decision-making processes. These factors can limit the overall effectiveness of their regulatory environments, impacting economic growth and global competitiveness. At the bottom of the ranking, many developing countries, such as Zimbabwe (38.5), Egypt (37.6), and Mozambique (32.6), struggle with maintaining effective regulatory frameworks. These countries face structural issues such as corruption, political instability, and lack of transparency, which hinder economic development and limit their attractiveness for foreign investment. In summary, the data highlights a stark difference between countries with well-developed regulatory systems and those where governance and institutions are weak. Countries with the highest scores tend to be those that have invested in transparent governance and stable institutions, while those with lower scores face significant challenges in improving their regulatory and governance capacities—factors that are essential for supporting long-term economic development and growth.

Regulatory Environment between 2013 and 2022. The data on the regulatory environment of various countries between 2013 and 2022 shows significant changes, highlighting both improvements and deteriorations in different regions. The regulatory environment is a crucial aspect of a country's economic climate, influencing investments, economic growth, and ease of doing business. By analyzing these changes, it is possible to understand which countries have improved their regulatory frameworks and which have faced difficulties. Countries like Angola, Portugal, and Indonesia have shown significant improvements in their regulatory environments. Angola, with a remarkable increase of 43.54%, demonstrates substantial efforts to reform its regulations, likely aiming to attract more foreign investments and foster economic growth. This growth can be attributed to increased political stability and economic reforms focused on improving transparency and competitiveness. Portugal, with an increase of 29.34%, has likely benefited from the economic reforms implemented after the European financial crisis. These reforms have facilitated trade and investment, improved labor market regulation, and simplified bureaucracy. Indonesia also saw positive progress (+23.16%), likely due to initiatives aimed at improving the business environment, reducing bureaucracy, and encouraging both local and foreign investments. Other countries, such as Lithuania (+17.56%), Azerbaijan (+16.73%), and Nigeria (+15.82%), have shown less marked but still significant growth. Lithuania, for instance, has continued to strengthen its regulatory framework, particularly after joining the European Union, thereby boosting investor confidence. Azerbaijan, a nation rich in energy resources, has likely benefited from regulatory improvements to attract foreign investment and diversify its economy. Nigeria, despite facing challenges related to security and governance, has made progress in improving regulations to stimulate economic activity, particularly in the infrastructure sector. On the other hand, some countries have experienced notable declines in their regulatory environments. Oman, with a decline of 26.70%, and Yemen, with a loss of 25.06%, reflect the difficulties arising from political instability and internal conflicts. These factors have had a devastating impact on the effectiveness of their regulatory frameworks, reducing investor confidence and hindering economic growth. Even advanced countries like Ireland (-11.87%) and Belgium (-14.77%) have seen significant declines. These drops may be related to internal economic or political difficulties that negatively impacted regulation, despite their traditional role as global economic leaders. For example, political crises and delays in economic reforms may have contributed to a perception of a deteriorating business environment. Additionally, countries like the United States (-5.50%) and the United Kingdom (-5.54%) have also seen declines in their regulatory environments. Although their economies are among the largest in the world, factors such as political uncertainty and

changes in economic policies may have contributed to a worsening perception of their regulations. The data shows a clear diversification in the evolution of regulatory environments globally. While some emerging countries have made significant strides in improving their regulatory contexts, others, especially those affected by conflicts or political crises, have experienced serious setbacks. At the same time, even some advanced economies have shown signs of weakening, indicating that maintaining a competitive regulatory environment requires continuous reforms and adaptation to global changes.

Conclusions. The value of the regulatory environment decreased on average by 2.44% for countries between 2013 and 2022, dropping from 67.2 units to 65.5 units. The top performers are: Angola with +43.54%, Portugal with +29.34%, Indonesia with +23.16%, Lithuania with +17.56%, and Azerbaijan with +16.73%. The worst performers are: Mozambique with -14.66%, Belgium with -14.77%, Tunisia with -15.10%, Yemen with -25.06%, and Oman with -26.70%.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performance	Angola	35,6	51,1	15,5	43,54
	Portugal	59,3	76,7	17,4	29,34
	Indonesia	17,7	21,8	4,1	23,16
	Lithuania	68,9	81	12,1	17,56
	Azerbaijan	52	60,7	8,7	16,73
Worse Performance	Mozambique	38,2	32,6	-5,6	-14,66
	Belgium	92,1	78,5	-13,6	-14,77
	Tunisia	68,2	57,9	-10,3	-15,10
	Yemen, Rep.	41,1	30,8	-10,3	-25,06
	Oman	80,9	59,3	-21,6	-26,70

Fonte: *Global Innovation Index*

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/web/global-innovation-index>

References

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR) e-ISSN*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Angelo, L., & Matarrese, M. M. (2023). The intellectual assets in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 27(2), 1-13.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach. *Applied econometrics and international development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN 4021150.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

